

Exploring Hyperbole in War Discourse: Netanyahu's Speech as a Sample Exploring

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Abstract

For politicians, using hyperbolic expressions seem to be an essential technique to use in their communications on various levels. It has important role in maintaining arguments in defending their accomplishments and/or criticizing the actions of their counterparts. This technique has been used by the Israeli prime minister, Benjamin Netanyahu in his reflections on the attacks of 7th October, 2023. The employment of this technique is derived from its importance in highlighting the emotional concerns of causalities as well as its great importance in swaying the public opinion and gathering support of both the internal and international societies. The present study aims to investigate the power dynamics and ideology that lay behind using hyperbole in the speech of Netanyahu adopting van Dijk's Framework of political discourse analysis (2008). The present study is qualitative in nature. It seeks to dig deep within Netanyahu's discourse to understand the underlying ideology behind using exaggerative utterances in describing the attacks of Hamas on Isreal. The study has concluded that the Israeli prime minister employed this discursive device to stimulate the emotional aspects of the audience to gain sympathy and support, negatively represent Hamas, and positively represent Isreal.

Keywords: *hyperbole, Netanyahu, van Dijk, Hamas, 7th October attacks.*

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Introduction

Political discourse analysis (PDA) is interested in the way language and politics affect each other and shape the public opinions, and other political processes and communication. Hyperbole, a discursive device that refers to the use of exaggerative language, is usually employed by politicians in their reflections on their deeds or the pitfalls of their counterparts shaping the perception of their audience in a way that serves their interests and ideology. Such expressions are employed in their speeches to maintain their messages and stimulate public opinion. Considering hyperbole, the present study examines how exaggerated language helps to distort facts and deceive perceptions. This, in turn, illustrates the power dynamics, ideology and communication tactics behind hyperbolic language. Binjamin Natenyahu employed hyperbole to face the new by the Israeli prime minister in his reflection of the Israel- Palestine conflict so as to maintain the understanding of how language reflects power dynamics. The present study seeks to contribute to the field of PDA by examining an important discursive rhetorical strategy which is employed to represent Isreal at war time.

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Political Discourse Analysis (PDA)

As politics represents a field of great impact and attachment with modern man's life, PDA presents itself as a promising subfield of discourse analysis to highlight the importance of language for both politicians and societies. Van Dijk's articles within this field present a comprehensive view of the role of language in social interactions and the underlying effects it has on these interactions with special consideration of cognitive processes like power and ideology. It also helps to understand the multidisciplinary nature of discourse analysis in considering the relation that holds language and society. A language user's linguistic choices shape and could be shaped by social interactions, power dynamics and relations. Here comes the role of discourse to consider these choices to reach a macro view of discourse highlighting their social, cultural and political context of the interaction process. Such investigation brings a wide view of several disciplines like sociology, politics, and anthropology beside linguistics. It provides a holistic view of the way language affects and is being affected by these dimensions (van Dijk, 2008).

Dallmar (1991) presented a careful insight into the process of interaction that specifies the structure of political representation. Through challenging the traditional view that sees political discourse confined to formal institutions and elites, Dallmar sheds light on the variety of perspectives that contribute to the convention of democratic dialogue. He argues that subordinated groups and social structures have vital roles in politics bringing up issues that are usually neglected or silenced (Dallmar, 1991).

Fairclough and Fairclough (2012) demonstrate that Political Discourse Analysis (PDA) is concerned with examining political discourse critically to reach better understanding. Through this, he sheds light on how political power is both reproduced and challenged by the expression of political discourse. Both Fairclough and van Dijk agree that political discourse is associated with variable political actors, such as politicians and/or ordinary citizens beside the political institutions and organizations. Those actors are involved in political processes and events. The priority is given to the consideration of the social and political aspects in which the communication takes place besides the way power is practiced through language. Through utilizing texts analysis and considering sociocultural context, they aim at revealing the underlying ideology and power dynamics which shape and are shaped by the communication process. The major concern of their discursive framework is to take in consideration three main and interrelated dimensions: text, representation, and social practice. Concerning the text, there should be an analysis of the linguistic aspects and structures that are provided within the discourse, like lexical choice, metaphor, and rhetorical devices. For representation, the analyst needs to consider the way language presents a specific view of the surrounding world, including the depiction of others. For the last aspect, social practice, there should be a consideration of the way social actors use the language to interact in accordance with certain events, people and issues. (Fairclough & Fairclough, 2012).

PDA indicates to the examination and analysis of the discourse language used by politicians for political purposes which include, but not specific for, the way politicians shape and deliver their political messages expressing power dynamics and ideological views that lie behind these messages, offering better understanding of the way language works to communicate and construct political realities. Besides that, it offers a good opportunity to explore the discourse as a practice that maps political views, identities, or even conflicts. Thus, PDA explores the roles the language plays in the world of politics, and the political images it simulates or is being simulated by (Mouffe & Laclau, 2001).

Political discourse has a great impact on societies for several reasons. Firstly, it is the primary way of communication which politicians use to express their values system, policies, stances and after all their ideology. Analysing political discourse could help to have clearer insights into the strategies, rhetoric, and messaging delivered by politicians. Additionally, it helps to reveal underlying biases, inconsistencies or even contradictions produced by political figures or organizations showing their cultural, social and ideological aspects and reflections. Moreover, it helps to investigate the role of media and the feedback of the reception of political messages to be better equipped with tools to interpret political communication, uncover manipulation, and have a critical understanding of political debates (Taylor, 2013).

The Concept of Hyperbole

As Fairclough proposed, a strong relationship between language and society is usually available in the field of political discourse specifically. Due to the fact that language is the major mean of interaction and communication, it plays undisputed role in (re)shaping social norms, relations, views as well as power dynamics. For Political speech, language has a crucial impact on persuading, mobilizing, and legitimizing political actions and policies. Analyzing a political discourse helps to provide insight into the underlying ideology, views, or even agendas of that political speech. It also reveals the way language is used strategically in structure realities, sway or shape public opinion, and maintain or challenge the certain power constructions. Moreover, doing a political discourse analysis provides insights into the mechanisms and norms of power practices within socio-cultural platform. Language can be employed in creating or maintaining dominance through the employment of lexical choices, rhetorical devices, and discursive strategies in the political discourse. Power relations and dominance, through language use among several dimensions, can be maintained, manipulated, and represented since language is not merely a reflection of social structures rather, language is powerful enough to create changes in these structures. Officials by their political discourse could mobilize individuals, challenge others' ideologies, and make social changes. (Fairclough & Fairclough, 2012)

As a powerful and familiar rhetorical device employed in political discourse, Hyperbole, which is originated from the Greek word for "exaggeration, is a figure of speech that is used to show emphasis or argue a point more dramatically. Claridge (2010) promoted the use of hyperbole in our daily conversation, showing how this rhetorical device is an unforgettable part of the language user's expressive knowledge. It is usually employed to make a situation or an event charged with emotions through exaggeration in some aspects or a lexical extreme. Using hyperbole, language users do not look for accuracy, instead, they aim to draw a picture that is over-the-top, almost unreal. Claridge mentioned some key features of hyperbole: exaggeration, intention to emphasize, engaging, memorable, common in everyday language, expressive and dramatic. Hyperbole goes beyond literal meaning, making things out of proportion showing how extreme a situation or feeling can be. Among reasons of using hyperbole are to assert a point, make something distinguished, or express a strong impression. It is just like turning up the volume of one's feelings and ideas to make them really recognizable. It makes a statement or story more powerful. One could use hyperbole without even realizing that. Such exaggeration could add color and emotion to the conversations, writing, or storytelling (Claridge,2010).

The term hyperbole is a figure of speech used to exaggerate or overstate so as to create emphasis or dramatic effect. It has several features: first, it has the tendency of being exaggerated and not literally true. This indicates that hyperbole intentionally exaggerates something for certain discursive reason. On a wider horizon, hyperbole allows speakers to make their argument or point more vivid and memorable. It grasps the audience's attention by shedding emphasis and making a point more impactful. second, hyperbole is characterized by being gradable, that is the exaggeration is varying to different degrees. Gradability adds layers of exaggeration by making the intensity of the exaggeration adjustable. This feature enables the speaker or writer to be free to choose the level of emphasis they want to place on something. Such flexibility opens the gates for a creative and expressive use of language to convey a point in the way they like. Third, Subjectivity is another feature of hyperbole that indicates conveying exaggerated language based on personal feelings or opinion. Speakers could express a subjective viewpoint depending on the context and their intention bringing emphasis, humor, or drama. Fourth, Hyperbole's feature of intentionality encompasses the conscious and deliberate usage of exaggeration so as to create a specific effect. In political speeches, hyperbole is usually employed by officials to make a point, emphasize a feeling, or praise an accomplishment. It enables them to captivate the public attention and evoke specific emotions by highlighting particular ideas or situations (Cruise,2017).

Within the context of wars and conflicts, hyperbole is usually employed to motivate emotions, charge and affect public perception. Through the exaggerated language, politicians could evoke effective reactions and shape attitudes towards war. Hyperbole could also be utilized in visual representation and sociocultural spectacle related to war. Hyperbolic expressions and overstatement could be effectively

used to convey powerful messages. Those hyperbolic depictions contribute to the construction of narratives about war shaping the public point of view concerning the conflict (Greenbaum, 2016).

Political leaders usually employ hyperbole to convey their ideology and political opinions as superior to those of their opponents, appealing to the values and emotions of their people as well as creating a sense of urgency or crisis. A political leader may use hyperbolic language to shed light on the dangers of a particular policy or to indicate that their own policy as the unique solution of a problem. Doing so, they aim to convince the audience to support their stance. It plays an important role in the subjective argumentations of the politicians expressing their attitudes about certain issue in order to gain the sympathy and attention of the audience towards their side showing more positivity of 'our' ideology and/or more negativity for 'their' ideology (van Dijk, 1993).

Hyperbole could help politicians to gain the audience's attention creating a sense of drama. Nevertheless, it could also be misleading or misunderstood if they use it excessively. Rhetorical questions represent a good example of hyperbole in political discourse as they are not delivered to be answered, rather, they are said to assert certain point evoking an emotional response in the audience (van Dijk, 1993).

The Essence of Hyperbole

As mentioned earlier, Politicians might employ hyperbole in order to create a sense of crisis or urgency. For instance, they may exaggerate the consequences of certain policy and/or the benefits of adopting their policy. Such strategy could be efficient in persuading the audience to support his/her stance though it could also be misleading if it is not employed well with factual evidence.

George Lakoff (2008) sees that hyperbole could function in the political interactions in variable ways and for variable purposes. Amplifying or overstating specific aspects of a message, politicians could capture attention, stir emotions, and create a sense of urgency or importance concerning a given issue. Through strategically use of hyperbole, politicians could shape realities, sway or maintain public opinion, and gather supporters for their side or agenda. Furthermore, he asserted the crystallization of power dynamics through using hyperbole within political discourse. Hyperbole highlights the importance of certain ideas or events, assert authority, establish credibility, and position the politician as a leader or an expert in particular issue. This does not help to maintain existing beliefs and ideology of their followers only but also works on persuading other marginal individuals or even sway the supporters of the opponents through the exaggerative presentations of arguments and topics showing their argument as the best for the presented issue. In addition, it acts as a tool that could be used to establish and maintain ideologies though repeated exaggerations of certain dimensions or concepts. Producing discourses with hyperbolic language, politicians could construct their discourse and engagement as well as turning conversations in the directions that meet their views or objectives. hyperbole acts as significant tool for directing political issues and shaping public opinion in a way that serves specific ideology and worldview (Lakoff,2008).

Van Emeren et.al. (2022) highlighted using hyperbole in the political domain, focusing on the intention behind hyperbolic and exaggerative utterances by politicians that sway or maintain the public opinion and reaction of their audience. In order to find out examples of hyperbole, a political discourse analyst needs to go deep in the language that goes beyond the scope of reason and accuracy. With a careful examination and analysis , they explore the use of rhetorical expressions, emotional declarations as well as vivid metaphors. They need to take in their consideration the significant role of context and the socio-cultural norms surrounding the discourse to reveal instances of hyperbolic language. This is done by having a careful and detailed evaluation of rhetorical devices and careful assessment of the construction of the discourse.

The impact of hyperbole seems to be highly significant in certain political issues if it is employed carefully. It could help to initiate several actions or reactions among the public. Discourses of war, of example, could be filled with hyperbolic expressions showing the heroism of 'our' army and/or the savagery of 'their' army. This, in turn, would create a sense of enthusiasm, support, and joy for 'our' accomplishments and/or hatred, sorrow, and disappointment for 'their' behavior. Politicians tend to be very selective in their descriptive statements or words that are used to refer to each party of the conflict.

Palestine-Israel Conflict

The history of the ongoing conflict between Palestine with the involvement of Hamas, a Palestinian armed movement, is a long one which goes back to the earliest of the 20th century having historical and geopolitical factors led to it. The Zionist movement aimed to initiate a home for Jews in Palestine. Zionism had received approval for their claim from the British government through the Balfour Declaration that paved the way for establishing Israel, but this declaration had been resisted by the Palestinian who refused the deal of giving their land to the Jews. However, this did not prevent them from applying their plan as they facilitated the massive migrations of Jews from different countries to be located in Palestine to announce the establishment of their country in 1948. Since its establishment, Israel faced constant challenges in securing the lands under their authority as they displaced so many Palestinians from their homes igniting the flames of conflict of trying to have control over the land. Hamas, a political and public military organization in Gaza which is designated as a terrorist organization by the Western countries, has further increased the conflict as it took the military reactions for what it considers as a Zionist occupation. This movement has been involved in rocket attacks and suicide bombings against Israel. This conflict has local and regional consequences. The recurrent wars, military confrontations, and violence have left permanent suffering and loss of lives on both sides. In addition, it has pinched diplomatic relations among regional and international powers, who tried to solve the problem for many years. International meditations have been done to set a peaceful resolution, including bilateral negotiations, international initiatives to temporarily or permanently ceasefires (Bunton,2013).

In the early morning of 7th October 2023, Hamas launched massive attack with 2,500 rockets followed by cyberattacks and drones to disrupt Israeli military communication which enabled 3000 to 5000 members of Hamas to cross into the Israeli areas (Wurmser et.al, 2024)

Methodology

The current study includes a qualitative analysis approach for the speech of the Israeli prime minister Benjamin Netanyahu shedding light on the text only regardless any other dimensions. The key elements of the analysis methodology are:

1. Identifying hyperbolic expressions: through examining the speech of the Israeli prime minister, the methodology includes identifying hyperbolic expressions used to talk about the crisis of 7th October 2023.
2. Interpretation and Contextualization: The present study focuses on the interpretation of the hyperbolic expressions under analysis within their context. This process requires comprehending the history of the conflict and power dynamics so that to reach better understanding of Netanyahu's statement.
3. Purpose and Effectiveness: The study tries to identify the expected objective behind Netanyahu's employment of hyperbole such as gaining local and international sympathy, showing strength or controlling the public opinion. In addition, it seeks to evaluate the efficiency of using it in achieving these objectives.
4. Ethical Consideration: The study is committed to the ethical guidelines concerning the use of political statements by official figures, ensuring that the analysis is done with objective integrity.
5. Critical Reflection: the study also includes critical reflection of the possible outcomes related to the analysis of political statements including subjective understanding to reach a balanced judgment for the impact and reasons behind employing hyperbolic language in war discourse.

Data Collection Methodology

The data of the present study is limited to a political statement presented by the current prime minister of Israel, Benjamin Netanyahu who delivered it in English language in the press conference that was held

in the margins of UN meeting in 9th October, 2023, two days after the attack of Hamas. This statement is retrieved by the researcher on YouTube channel named "Israelism" on February 14, 2024. The video of the statement carried the title "Statement by Prime Minister Benjamin". The meeting aimed to discuss the current crisis in Israel and the potential solutions.

Data Analysis

The present section is devoted to examine the utterances that are mentioned in Netanyahu's statement. These utterances are numerated ascendingly according to their position in the statement:

1. "Israel is at war"

This utterance contains hyperbole as the prime minister described the way he looks at these attacks, "at war". He intended to describe the stance of Israel of these attacks showing that they would not stand with folded hands, rather, they are and will defend themselves against these attacks. In addition, this utterance could be interpreted in the context of potential threat to Israel calling for urgency to get ready to face this situation.

2. "It was forced upon us in the most brutal and savage way."

Netanyahu here recalls several issues by mentioning that this war is forced on Israel to point out that they seek peace with Palestine. He denied the recurrent attacks of Israeli soldiers on the Palestinians in Gaza. He tries to turn the compass of the public opinion both locally and internationally to portray Israel as being innocent and oppressed who looks for secure life. However, their peaceful life is threatened by these "brutal and savage" attacks.

3. "But though Israel didn't start this war, Israel will finish it."

Here, Netanyahu expressed the power dynamics of the conflict. He showed how strong position Israel has in this combat assuring that they control the war to finish it for their favor. Netanyahu, through delivering such expression, tries to sway the public opinion that the Israeli government has a peaceful nature as a one that do not initiate war or conflict and at the same time it has the power to defend itself against any attack in the way they like.

4. "Hamas will understand that by attacking us, they have made a mistake of historic proportions."

Netanyahu goes further to threaten Hamas that they committed a very big mistake whose consequences and impact will last long to the extent that these consequences would be recorded in the history of the two sides. Netanyahu here, through such hyperbolic description, sends a determinant message to Hamas that the Israeli reply would not be limited to defend itself, rather, they would create historical changes on the ground and this seemed to be the situation as the Israeli army attacked the Palestinian areas and swept away several houses and displaced the civilians from wide areas. He throws the blame on Hamas for their attack caused these historical events.

5. "We will exact a price that will be remembered by them and Israel's other enemies for decades to come."

Netanyahu goes on to threaten the other enemies of Israel not to do as what Hamas did pointing that this action of initiating war against Israel will stick in their minds for decades. He aims to project an image of power, deterrence and strength conveying a message of warning to the surrounding enemies that they would regret attacking Israel due to the consequences they will have out of the scenario of confrontation.

6. "The savage attacks that Hamas perpetrated against innocent Israelis are mindboggling."

Netanyahu, here, used two radical descriptions through hyperbolic language: the first one is his description of Hamas' attacks as being savage which indicate that they are barbarians and against humanity. On the other hand, he described Israelis as being innocent. This indicates that they are good people and guiltless. He tries to sway the public opinion both locally and more importantly internationally

through portraying the conflict as being between 'their' savagery and 'our' innocence. He also aims to present emotional stimulation to gain their support.

7. "Massacring hundreds of young people at an outdoor festival."

Netanyahu gave a hyperbolic utterance as a proof of his claim of describing Hamas as a savage organization that killed a large number of innocent people. The employment of the word "Massacring" indicates exaggeration of the Israeli casualties evoking a sense of sympathy, outrage and shock to emphasize how sever and tragic this event was. It seems that Netanyahu exaggerated to create this image of killers- victims relationship. The later were enjoying a festival outdoor as evidence of their normal life.

8. "Kidnapping scores of women, children, and elderly, even Holocaust survivors."

To gain more support and sympathy of the public opinion, Netanyahu goes further in drawing the image of savagery-innocence by highlighting the idea of kidnapping enormous number of civilians. This process included women, children and old people. It even included survivors from the Holocaust. This hyperbolic expression sheds light on kidnappings and asserts the urgency of addressing it seriously. He included the weak categories of the Israeli society ending up with addressing the Holocaust. Netanyahu successfully made a connection between what Hamas does and what Hitler did with the Jews to gain the emotional support of the international community

9. "Hamas' terrorists bound, burned, and executed children."

Netanyahu, here, describes the members of Hamas as terrorists rather than land defenders. He goes further by using emotionally charged vocabularies linking them with children, the most innocent individuals. He seeks to create emotional shock portraying Hamas as the ultimate violent organization.

10. "They are savages. Hamas is ISIS."

Using hyperbolic language here might serve some discursive purposes. First, repeating the word "savage" conforms this assumption in the mind of the perceivers about Hamas. He presents Hamas as inhumane group that is engaged in brutal behavior. Second, through describing Hamas as ISIS, He attempts to assert the idea of savagery. ISIS is an ultimately violent organization. Making this direct linkage between Hamas and ISIS, he tries to aims to shed light on severity of the expected treats of Hamas swaying the opinion of the audience that both organizations represent the two faces of the same coin. He looks for invoking emotional trauma. Besides that, such utterance acts as a justification for the aggressive reaction of Israel and stimulates support to take actual measures to face them.

11. "In fighting Hamas, Israel is not only fighting for its own people' It is fighting for every country that stands against barbarism."

By suggesting that their fight against Hamas is not merely for their own sake but on the behalf of every country, Netanyahu conveys that they fight the extreme ideology of violence that does not threat Israel alone but also the international peace and security. he seeks to convey the idea that this battle represents a larger conflict against extremist ideologies and acts of violence that threaten global peace and security. He also tries to sway the international opinion by considering the countries that support Israel as being against barbarism and those who support Palestine as being barbarians. Through framing this conflict in this way, the aims at triggering sympathy and help from the countries that describes themselves as democratic and peace lovers. Besides that, such hyperbolic language calls for urgency to stand with Israel against this organization that threatens the international security of the globe.

12. "Israel will win this war, and when Israel wins, the entire civilized world wins."

Once again, Netanyahu claims that those who support Israel are civilized while those who stand with Hamas and Palestine are barbarians. He also claims that Israel will win in this conflict and this winning will be attributed to entire civilized world since they support Israel. This might serve as a call for every nation to consider Israel as a strong ally that sooner or later will win this conflict for the sake of global peace.

13. "I want to thank President Biden for his unequivocal support."

In this utterance, Netanyahu suggests that the president of USA, Joe Biden presented limitless and absolute support for Israel. Doing so, he points out that the president of one of the strongest countries around the world is standing with Israel. Such expression of gratitude serves as an announcement for the countries that ally with USA to stand with Israel and a warning for the others that 'we' are not alone, America is standing with 'us'.

The bottom line of this speech is that Netanyahu tries to portray his country as a strong and resolute one that stands against aggression and violence. He implies that they are determinant to achieve victory though they did not start the war but they will have the upper hand to finish it in the time and way they like, showing that what they did and will do are only actions of self-defense.

Netanyahu tried to create an image of how good and civilized 'we' are and how aggressive and violent 'they' are. He illustrated that Hamas members are savage and barbarians who killed and attacked innocent people from different age stages: children, old people, and women as well as Holocaust survivors seeking to evoke sympathy and support by showing Israel as a victim of this violence. He employed very strong language to show Hamas as the second face of ISIS which has extreme and savage nature beside implying that they have similar ideologies to delegitimize Hamas for the international community. This serves his attention to belittle Hamas and Palestine in one hand and strengthen the stance of Israel and gain support by symbolizing the conflict to be between "savagery" verses "innocence", "barbarism" verses "civilization", and "violence" verses "peace". He ends up his speech by retrieving his gratitude for the leaders of the world with special thanks to the president of USA showing that the strongest and developed countries stand with his country calling for more support from the rest of the "civilized" countries.

Conclusions

The present study has concluded the following:

1. The Israeli prime minister, Benjamin Netanyahu, has delivered an impassioned speech in which almost every word is dedicated to trigger emotions to sway the international community to be on the side of Israel in its conflict against Palestine and Hamas. The hyperbolic language is used to serve this purpose as he used emotions-charged words to describe both parties as well as the current and future scenarios.
2. He portrayed Hamas as being savage who akin to ISIS. This was not a mere name-calling, rather, it is coining these organizations to be the two faces of the same coin. Netanyahu sought to underscore the danger of these two organizations so as to gain sympathy and support both internally and most importantly externally. Netanyahu employed hyperbole to present Hamas as being the extreme terrorists who are savage, violent and barbarians intensifying the need for urgent decision-making to face them.
3. Retrieving the historical catastrophe of the Holocaust, Netanyahu made a poignant reminder to invoke the psychological- emotional dimension to imbued his speech with the historical misery that is infused with the present urgency.
4. Announcing that Israel would "finish" the war, Netanyahu expressed his determination and confidence about the outcome of this conflict. Such hyperbolic wording present Israel as undisputed power in the Middle East.
5. Expressing gratitude towards the president of USA serves as a strategic move to call the friends of America to ally with Israel against Palestine and Hamas. His hyperbolic description of Biden's support amplifies the significance of the international coalition with Israel.
6. Through the overt use of hyperbole, Netanyahu expresses a strong image for Israel in facing the developments of the Palestine-Israel conflict. He explicitly identified his decision of having actual reply that would be heavier than Hamas' attacks. This, in turn, maintains one of the main implementations of van Dijk's political discourse in reinforcing 'our' (re)actions and underestimating 'their' (re)actions. This

helps to sway or shape the public opinions of both local and international levels about the war discourse as well as the future reactions.

References

- Bunton, M. P. (2013). *The Palestinian-Israeli conflict: A very short introduction*. Oxford University Press.
- Claridge, C. (2010). *Hyperbole in English: A corpus-based study of exaggeration*. Cambridge University Press.
- Cruise, C. E. (2017). *Writing on the edge: Paul's use of hyperbole in Galatians*. Trinity International University.
- Dallmar, F. R. (1991). *Margins of political discourse*. SUNY Press.
- Fairclough, I., & Fairclough, N. (2012). *Political discourse analysis: A method for advanced students*. Routledge.
- Greenbaum, A. (2016). *The tropes of war: Visual hyperbole and spectacular culture*. Springer.
- Lakoff, G. (2008). *The political mind: A cognitive scientist's guide to your brain and its politics*. Penguin.
- Mouffe, C., & Laclau, E. (2001). *Hegemony and socialist strategy: Towards a radical democratic politics*. Verso.
- Taylor, S. (2013). *What is discourse analysis?* Wiley-Blackwell.
- van Dijk, T. A. (1993). *Principles of critical discourse analysis*. Sage.
- van Dijk, T. A. (2008). *Discourse and power*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- van Eemeren, F. H., Garssen, B., Greco, S., van Haften, T., Labrie, N., Leal, F., & Wu, P. (2022). *Argumentative style: A pragma-dialectical study of functional variety in argumentative discourse*. John Benjamins.
- Wurmser, D., Waller, M., Illarionov, A., & Shideler, K. (2024). *Case study: Hamas' October 7, 2023 attack on Israel*. Center for Security Policy.

